
QURANIC TRANSLATIONS IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE (CLASSIFICATION, OBJECTIVES & PREREQUISITES)

Dr. Tahir Mahmood (ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5670-1824)

Member Darul Ifta, Jamia Darul Uloom Karachi.

Prof. Dr. Ubaid Ahmed Khan (ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5098-5643)

Professor, Department of Usooluddin, University of Karachi.

ABSTRACT

This research article deals with some technical aspects related to the translations of the Holy Quran in different languages, especially in the English language from a research point of view. The English language has become a global communication language due to several reasons. Therefore, like other languages, rather much more than them, authentic English translations of the Holy Quran must be translated by Muslim translators having the right beliefs and authentic religious knowledge to convey the message of Allah to the people in the English language. This is necessary because many incorrect translations have been produced by non-Muslim translators to propagate their false ideas. Therefore, in this research article, an introductory study of the translators, the classification of the Quranic translations, their types, objectives, and the prerequisites as the essential conditions required for it will be presented to get a better understanding of the scholarly discussions related to the topic.

Keywords: Quranic Translations, English, Classification, Objectives, Pre-requisites.

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